

ROLE PLAY AS A METHOD OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT: In this article important features of role play method, its types and functions were discussed. Moreover, positive impact of role play to the learners were noted.

KEY WORDS: emphasis, communicative ability, "rolled-up", styles – listening, "tapestry approach", "tension to learn", exploitation.

In recent years, language teaching has focused on the learning process rather than the teaching of the language. The emphasis is not only on linguistic competence of the language learners but also on the development of their communicative ability. In order to develop the learners' communicative ability, the teacher needs to create a scenario to teach the target language in a vibrant, active and interesting manner. Many English teachers are exploring and attempting new and innovative practices in the classroom. They have turned to dialogues, open-ended scenarios, and role plays.

Extended activities in the form of role play, simulations and problem solving are vital in developing the communicative ability of the learners. These activities require the learners to go beyond a text. They require the learners to have a sound understanding of a text and be able to apply their knowledge outside the classroom and their own experiences into the activities. The term "role" comes from the "rolled-up" script actors used to use over two thousand years ago in Ancient Greece. In time, the script became the part, and actors then were said to play the "role" of, say, Hamlet or Othello or Ophelia or Desdemona. But one can also create a role, improvise a performance, and in fact children do this all the time in their pretend play. There's a kind of vitality that attends this type of

imaginative activity. Jacob L. Moreno (1889-1974) discovered that the activity of dramatic improvisation was therapeutic for his actors, and began to think about applying this approach as a type of individual and family treatment. Moreno had a most fertile mind, and wove together many associated ideas about social psychology and group dynamics. He was one of the pioneers of group psychotherapy and even engaged in his own type of philosophy, emphasizing the need for appreciating the fundamental importance of creativity in life. One aspect of role playing was that of diagnosis or assessment—a test of how a person would act when placed in an imagined or pretend problematic situation.

There can be two ways of looking at language work in similar role plays and role playing games: the pupils manage with the language they already know or they practice with structures and functions that have been presented in an earlier part of the lesson, another way, and the pupils can only benefit from the experience. There are many types of role plays which can be used in primary school classrooms. The goal of all of these methods is to engage junior learners in real world thinking and problem solving. One type is called "option display." This method works well for situations where a controversial issue is being addressed where the answer is not very clear. The procedure would be to list the problem/question then construct a display with possible solutions and decide on the proper solution. In a situation like this, pupils can be given role assignments by their teacher; in doing this, the learner is then forced to see the issue as best they can through the eyes of an individual affected by this in a different way from themselves.

Role play is often chosen for creating a situation for junior learners to actively interact in the language, thereby making the language learning more meaningful. At the same time, the learners are introduced to the different learning styles - listening, remembering, discussing, writing and presenting. Role-playing is useful for practicing appropriate behavior in more complex social interactions where students must choose from a wide range of possible behaviors. Good topics for role-playing include sharing materials, including classmates in activities, and supporting someone who makes a mistake. Role-playing allows the teacher to acknowledge the complexity of these situations and give students practice in making responsible choices.

Traditionally, learner roles have been specifically defined in the role playing method, either through verbal instructions or role cards. However, Kaplan (1997) argues against role-plays that focus solely on prescriptive themes emphasizing specific fields of vocabulary, as they do not capture the spontaneous, real-life flow of conversation. Perhaps a better model for learner roles in the role playing method is Scarcella (1992) "tapestry approach". Learners, according to this approach, should be active and have considerable control over their own learning. The pupils should help select themes and tasks and provide teachers with details of their learning process. In role playing, this can be achieved through the "design competition" mentioned above, or similar "divergent" simulations. Pupils have some new responsibilities in role playing that they might not be accustomed to. Burns and Gentry (1998), looking at undergraduates learning experientially, suggest that some have not been exposed to experiences requiring them to be proactive and to make decisions in unfamiliar contexts. They recommend that instructors understand the knowledge level that learners bring to the scene, and place close attention to the introduction of experiential exercises so that the student does not become discouraged.

The teacher defines the general structure of the role play, but generally does not actively participate once the structure is set. To quote Jones (1982), "...the teacher becomes the Controller, and controls the event in the same way as a traffic controller, helping the flow of traffic and avoiding bottlenecks, but not telling individuals which way to go." Again, this is consistent with Scarcella (1992) principles. Rather than a traditional, teacher-centered classroom structure, the teacher keeps a relatively low profile and pupils are free to interact with each other spontaneously. This reduces pupil's anxiety and facilitates learning. The teacher must take on some additional responsibilities in role playing. In particular, the teacher must keep learners motivated by stimulating their curiosity and keeping the material relevant, creating, so called, a "tension to learn". As role play represent real-world scenarios, materials should simulate the materials that would be used in the real world. For example, blocks or sugar cubes can be employed in simulating a construction task. In the "extraterrestrial" role play, toothbrushes, watches, light bulbs and keys can be examined by the "aliens."

To sum up all facts above it should be noted that language teaching can be an interesting challenge when teachers make the effort to explore a variety of approaches. Role play is just one of the many methods available for exploitation. With some attention given to the needs of the learners, both the teacher and the learners can play active roles in the classroom, making language classes livelier, challenging and above all rewarding. So, role play increases motivation. Always talking about real life can become very dull, and the chance to imagine different situations adds interest to a lesson. Role play gives a chance to use language in new contexts and for new topics. Children and even teenagers and adults often imagine themselves in different situations and roles when they play games. So by using role play in class teachers are building on something that learners naturally enjoy. It is effective method of teaching foreign language young learners because 'fun' must be the most important part in teaching them.

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